

HEIGHTS IN FINITE PROJECTIVE SPACE, AND A PROBLEM ON DIRECTED GRAPHS

Melvyn B. Nathanson¹

Department of Mathematics, Lehman College (CUNY), Bronx, New York 10468
 melvyn.nathanson@lehman.cuny.edu

Blair D. Sullivan²

Department of Mathematics, Princeton University, Princeton, New Jersey 08544
 bdowling@princeton.edu

Received: 6/14/07, Revised: 3/25/08, Accepted: 4/3/08, Published: 4/9/08

Abstract

Let $\mathbb{F}_p = \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$. The *height* of a point $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_d) \in \mathbb{F}_p^d$ is

$$h_p(\mathbf{a}) = \min \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) : k = 1, \dots, p-1 \right\}.$$

Explicit formulas and estimates are obtained for the values of the height function in the case $d = 2$, and these results are applied to the problem of determining the minimum number of edges that must be deleted from a finite directed graph so that the resulting subgraph is acyclic.

1. Heights in Finite Projective Space

Let F be a field and let $F^* = F \setminus \{0\}$. For $d \geq 2$, we define an equivalence relation on the set of nonzero d -tuples $F^d \setminus \{(0, \dots, 0)\}$ as follows: $(a_1, \dots, a_d) \sim (b_1, \dots, b_d)$ if there exists $k \in F^*$ such that $(b_1, \dots, b_d) = (ka_1, \dots, ka_d)$. We denote the equivalence class of (a_1, \dots, a_d) by $\langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle$. The set of equivalence classes is called the $(d-1)$ -dimensional projective space over the field F , and denoted $\mathbb{P}^{d-1}(F)$.

We consider projective space over the finite field $\mathbb{F}_p = \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$. For every $x \in \mathbb{F}_p$, we denote by $x \pmod p$ the least nonnegative integer in the congruence class x . We define the *height* of the point $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$ by $h_p(\mathbf{a}) = \min \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) : k = 1, \dots, p-1 \right\}$.

¹The work of M.B.N. was supported in part by grants from the NSA Mathematical Sciences Program and the PSC-CUNY Research Award Program.

²The work of B.D. S. was supported in part by a Department of Homeland Security Dissertation Grant.

For every nonempty set $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$, we define $H_p(\mathcal{A}) = \{h_p(\mathbf{a}) : \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}\}$. Then $H_p(\mathcal{A})$ is a set of positive integers.

For $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$, let $d^*(\mathbf{a})$ denote the number of nonzero components of \mathbf{a} , that is, the number of $a_i \neq 0$. The function $d^*(\mathbf{a})$ is well-defined, that is, independent of the representative of the equivalence class of \mathbf{a} . For $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$, we define

$$d^*(\mathcal{A}) = \max\{d^*(\mathbf{a}) : \mathbf{a} \in \mathcal{A}\}.$$

Then $h_p(\mathbf{a}) \leq d^*(\mathbf{a})(p-1)$ for all $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$. We can reduce this upper bound by a simple averaging argument.

For every real number t , let $[t]$ denote the greatest integer not exceeding t .

Lemma 1. *For every point $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$, $h_p(\mathbf{a}) \leq \left\lfloor \frac{d^*(\mathbf{a})p}{2} \right\rfloor$.*

Proof. If $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$, then $\{ka \pmod p : k = 1, \dots, p-1\} = \{1, \dots, p-1\}$ and so

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (ka \pmod p) = \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} k = \frac{p(p-1)}{2}.$$

It follows that for every $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) = \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} (ka_i \pmod p) = \frac{d^*(\mathbf{a})p(p-1)}{2}.$$

Since the minimum of a set of numbers does not exceed the average of the set, we have

$$h_p(\mathbf{a}) \leq \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) = \frac{d^*(\mathbf{a})p}{2}.$$

The lemma follows from the fact that the heights are positive integers. \square

Lemma 2. *For every odd prime p and $d \geq 2$,*

$$\begin{aligned} \max(H_p(\mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p))) &= \frac{dp}{2} && \text{if } d \text{ is even} \\ \frac{(d-1)p}{2} + 1 &\leq \max(H_p(\mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p))) \leq \frac{dp-1}{2} && \text{if } d \text{ is odd.} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. If $2r \leq d$ and $a_1, \dots, a_r, a_{2r+1}, \dots, a_d$ are nonzero elements of the field \mathbb{F}_p , then the point $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r, -a_1, -a_2, \dots, -a_r, a_{2r+1}, \dots, a_d \rangle$, satisfies $d^*(\mathbf{a}) = d$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) &= \sum_{i=1}^r ((ka_i \pmod p) + (-ka_i \pmod p)) + \sum_{i=2r+1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) \\ &\geq rp + d - 2r \end{aligned}$$

for all $k = 1, \dots, p-1$. If $d-2r \leq p-1$, we can choose distinct elements a_{2r+1}, \dots, a_d and

$$\sum_{i=1}^d (ka_i \pmod p) \geq rp + \frac{(d-2r)(d-2r+1)}{2}.$$

Applying Lemma 1 and the inequality with $r = [d/2]$, we obtain $h_p(\mathbf{a}) = dp/2$ if d is even and $\frac{(d-1)p}{2} + 1 \leq h_p(\mathbf{a}) \leq \frac{dp-1}{2}$ if d is odd. This completes the proof. \square

2. Heights on the Finite Projective Line

The projective line $\mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)$ consists of all equivalence classes of pairs (a_1, a_2) , where $a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{F}_p$ and a_1 and a_2 are not both 0. If $a_1 = 0$, then $\langle 0, a_2 \rangle = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$ and $h_p(\langle 0, 1 \rangle) = 1$. If $a_2 = 0$, then $\langle a_1, 0 \rangle = \langle 1, 0 \rangle$ and $h_p(\langle 1, 0 \rangle) = 1$. If $a_1 \neq 0$ and $a_2 \neq 0$, then $\langle a_1, a_2 \rangle = \langle 1, a_1^{-1}a_2 \rangle$. Thus, for all $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)$, if $\mathbf{a} \neq \langle 1, 0 \rangle$ and $\mathbf{a} \neq \langle 0, 1 \rangle$, then $\mathbf{a} = \langle 1, a \rangle$ for some $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$, and $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \geq 2$.

Lemma 3. *Let p be an odd prime and $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$. Then*

- (i) $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq 1 + (a \bmod p)$ for all a ,
- (ii) $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = 1 + (a \bmod p)$ if $a \bmod p < \sqrt{p}$,
- (iii) $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = 2$ if and only if $a = 1 + p\mathbb{Z}$,
- (iv) $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = 3$ if and only if $a = 2 + p\mathbb{Z}$ or $a = (p + 1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}$,
- (v) $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = p$ if and only if $a = p - 1 + p\mathbb{Z}$,
- (vi) Let $a = p - b + p\mathbb{Z}$ for $1 \leq b \leq p - 1$. Then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq (p + (b - 1)^2) / b$.

Proof. For all $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, p - 1\}$ we have $ka \bmod p \in \{1, \dots, p - 1\}$, and so

$$h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = \min\{k + (ka \bmod p) : k = 1, \dots, p - 1\} \leq 1 + (a \bmod p).$$

Note that $ka \bmod p \leq k(a \bmod p)$ for all $k \geq 1$. If $k \geq a \bmod p$, then $k + (ka \bmod p) \geq (a \bmod p) + 1$. If $1 \leq k \leq (a \bmod p) - 1$ and $(a \bmod p) < \sqrt{p}$, then

$$ka \bmod p \leq k(a \bmod p) \leq ((a \bmod p) - 1)(a \bmod p) \leq (a \bmod p)^2 < p$$

It follows that $ka \bmod p = k(a \bmod p)$ and

$$k + (ka \bmod p) = k + k(a \bmod p) \geq 1 + (a \bmod p).$$

and so $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = 1 + (a \bmod p)$. This proves (i) and (ii).

We have $k + (ka \bmod p) = 2$ if and only if $k = 1$ and $ka \bmod p = a \bmod p = 1$, that is, $a = 1 + p\mathbb{Z}$. Similarly, $k + (ka \bmod p) = 3$ if and only if either $k = 1$ and $ka \bmod p = a \bmod p = 2$, or $k = 2$ and $ka \bmod p = 2a \bmod p = 1$. In the first case, $a = 2 + p\mathbb{Z}$ and, in the second case, $a = (p + 1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}$. This proves (iii) and (iv).

If $a = -1 + p\mathbb{Z}$, then $k + (ka \bmod p) = k + (p - k) = p$ for all $k = 1, \dots, p - 1$ and so $h_p(1, a) = p$. Conversely, if $h_p(1, a) = p$, then $k + (ka \bmod p) = p$ for some k , and so $ka \bmod p = -k \bmod p$ and $a = -1 + p\mathbb{Z}$. This proves (v).

Finally, to prove (vi), we let $p = qb + r$, where $q = [p/b]$ and $1 \leq r \leq p - 1$. Then

$$qa = \left[\frac{p}{b} \right] (p - b) + p\mathbb{Z} = p - \left[\frac{p}{b} \right] b + p\mathbb{Z} = r + p\mathbb{Z}$$

and so $qa \pmod p = r$. Therefore,

$$h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq q + r = \frac{p + r(b-1)}{b} \leq \frac{p + (b-1)^2}{b}.$$

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 1. *Let p be an odd prime and $a \in \mathbb{F}_p$. Then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = (p+1)/2$ if and only if $a = (p-1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}$ or $a = p-2 + p\mathbb{Z}$. If $a \notin \{(p-1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}, p-2 + p\mathbb{Z}, p-1 + p\mathbb{Z}\}$, then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$.*

Proof. The theorem is true for $p = 3, 5$, and 7 , so we can assume that $p \geq 11$. Let $a = p-2 + p\mathbb{Z}$. If $1 \leq k \leq (p-1)/2$, then

$$k + (ka \pmod p) = k + (p-2k) = p-k \geq \frac{p+1}{2}$$

and $k + (ka \pmod p) = (p+1)/2$ when $k = (p-1)/2$. If $k \geq (p+1)/2$, then $k + (ka \pmod p) \geq (p+3)/2$. Therefore, $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = (p+1)/2$.

Let $a = (p-1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}$. If $j = 1, \dots, (p-1)/2$ and $k = 2j$, then

$$k + (ka \pmod p) = 2j + (j(p-1) \pmod p) = 2j + (p-j) = p+j \geq p+1.$$

If $k = 2j-1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} k + (ka \pmod p) &= (2j-1) + \left(\frac{(2j-1)(p-1)}{2} \pmod p \right) \\ &= (2j-1) + \left(\frac{p+1}{2} - j \right) \\ &= \frac{p+2j-1}{2} \geq \frac{p+1}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $1 + (a \pmod p) = (p+1)/2$, it follows that $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = (p+1)/2$.

If $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ and $(a \pmod p) \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, (p-3)/2\}$, then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq 1 + (a \pmod p) \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$ by Lemma 3 (i). If $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ and $(a \pmod p) = (p+1)/2$, then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = 3 < (p+1)/2$ by Lemma 3 (iv).

Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$ and $(p+3)/2 \leq a \pmod p \leq p-3$. There is an integer b such that

$$3 \leq b \leq \frac{p-3}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad a = p-b + p\mathbb{Z}.$$

By Lemma 3 (vi) we have $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq (p + (b-1)^2)/b$, and so $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) \leq (p-1)/2$ if

$$2b+1 + \frac{4}{b-2} \leq p.$$

If $4 \leq b \leq (p-3)/2$, then $2b+1 + \frac{4}{b-2} \leq 2b+3 \leq p$. If $b=3$, then $h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle) = h_p(\langle 1, p-3 \rangle) \leq (p-1)/2$ since

$$2b+1 + \frac{4}{b-2} = 11 \leq p.$$

This completes the proof. \square

Table of Heights for Primes $11 \leq p \leq 29$

prime p	$a \pmod p$	$h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle)$	prime p	$a \pmod p$	$h_p(\langle 1, a \rangle)$
11	2	3	23	2	3
	3	4		3	4
	4	4		4	5
	5	6		5	6
	6	3		6	5
	7	5		7	8
	8	5		8	4
	9	6		9	7
	13	2		3	10
3		4		11	12
4		5		12	3
5		5		13	5
6		7		14	6
7		3		15	9
8		5		16	5
9		4		17	8
10		5		18	7
17	11	7		19	8
	2	3		20	9
	3	4		21	12
	4	5		29	2
	5	6	3		4
	6	4	4		5
	7	6	5		6
	8	9	6		6
	9	3	7		8
	10	5	8		7
	11	7	9		10
	12	5	10		4
	13	5	11		7
	14	7	12		7
	15	9	13		10
19	2	3	14		15
	3	4	15		3
	4	5	16		5
	5	5	17	7	
	6	7	18	8	
	7	5	19	11	
	8	7	20	5	
	9	10	21	8	
	10	3	22	5	
	11	5	23	9	
	12	7	24	9	
	13	4	25	8	
	14	7	26	11	
	15	7	27	15	
	16	7			
	17	10			

3. Problems on Heights

Problem 1. Let $d \geq 2$ and $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle \in \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$. Is there a simple formula to compute $h_p(\mathbf{a})$? Is there a simple formula to estimate $h_p(\mathbf{a})$? This is not known even for the projective line $d = 2$.

Problem 2. By Theorem 1 and Lemma 3, we have $H_p(\mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)) \cap \left(\frac{p+1}{2}, p\right) = \emptyset$. For which positive integers r does there exist a number c_r such that

$$H_p(\mathbb{P}^1(\mathbb{F}_p)) \cap \left(\frac{p}{r+1} + c_r, \frac{p}{r} - c_r\right) = \emptyset$$

for all sufficiently large p ?

Problem 3. Is there an upper bound for the heights of points in the projective plane $\mathbb{P}^2(\mathbb{F}_p)$ analogous to the upper bound in Theorem 1 for the projective line?

Problem 4. The following problem arises in graph theory. Let $k \geq 2$ and let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_p)$ be a nonempty subset of projective space such that

- (1) If $\mathbf{a} = \langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle \in \mathcal{A}$, then the coordinates a_i are pairwise distinct.
- (2) For $\ell = 1, \dots, k$, none of the equations $x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_\ell = 0$ has a solution with $x_1, \dots, x_k \in \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d\}$. (These conditions are homogeneous and independent of the representative of the equivalence class of \mathbf{a} .)

Find an upper bound for $H_p(\mathcal{A})$.

Problem 5. Find a good definition of the height of a point in the projective space $\mathbb{P}^{d-1}(\mathbb{F}_q)$ over any finite field \mathbb{F}_q .

4. Cayley Graphs with Vertex Set \mathbb{F}_p

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph with vertex set V and edge set $E \subseteq V \times V$. A *directed path* of length n in G is a sequence of vertices $v_{i_0}, v_{i_1}, v_{i_2}, \dots, v_{i_n}$ such that $(v_{i_j}, v_{i_{j+1}})$ is an edge for $j = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$. A *directed cycle* of length n in G is a directed path $v_{i_0}, v_{i_1}, v_{i_2}, \dots, v_{i_n}$ such that $v_{i_n} = v_{i_0}$. A *loop* is a directed cycle of length 1, a *digon* is a directed cycle of length 2, and a *triangle* is a directed cycle of length 3. A 3-free or triangle-free graph is a graph with no loop, digon, or triangle. The graph $G = (V, E)$ is called *directed acyclic* if it has no directed cycle.

The outdegree of the vertex v is the number of edges of the form (v, v') for some vertex v' . The pigeonhole principle implies that in a finite directed graph, if the outdegree of every vertex is at least 1, then the graph contains a cycle. Thus, every finite directed acyclic graph contains at least one vertex with outdegree 0.

Theorem 2. Let $\{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ be a set of m distinct integers, and let G be a finite directed graph with vertex set $V = \{v_{k_0}, v_{k_1}, \dots, v_{k_{m-1}}\}$. The graph G is directed acyclic if and only if there is a one-to-one map $\sigma : \{0, 1, \dots, m-1\} \rightarrow \{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ such that, if $(v_{\sigma(i)}, v_{\sigma(j)})$ is an edge of the graph, then $i < j$. If $\{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{m-1}\} = \{0, 1, \dots, m-1\}$,

then G is directed acyclic if and only if there is a permutation σ of $\{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$ such that $r < s$ for every edge $(v_{\sigma(r)}, v_{\sigma(s)})$ of the graph.

Proof. Let $\sigma : \{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\} \rightarrow \{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ be a one-to-one map such that, if $(v_{\sigma(i)}, v_{\sigma(j)})$ is an edge of the graph, then $i < j$. If $v_{\sigma(i_0)}, v_{\sigma(i_1)}, \dots, v_{\sigma(i_n)}$ is a path in G , then $i_0 < i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_n$ and so $i_n \neq i_0$, that is, $v_{\sigma(i_n)} \neq v_{\sigma(i_0)}$, and so no path in G is a cycle.

To prove the converse, we use induction on m . The Lemma holds for $m = 1$ and $m = 2$. Assume that $m \geq 2$ and that the lemma is true for every finite acyclic graph with m vertices. If G is an acyclic directed graph with $m + 1$ vertices $\{v_{k_0}, v_{k_1}, \dots, v_{k_m}\}$, then there exists a vertex v_{k_r} with outdegree 0. Consider the induced subgraph G' of G on the vertex set $\{v_{k_0}, v_{k_1}, \dots, v_{k_{r-1}}, v_{k_{r+1}}, \dots, v_{k_m}\}$. By the induction hypothesis, there is a one-to-one map σ' from $\{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$ into $\{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_{r-1}, k_{r+1}, \dots, k_m\}$ such that if $(v_{\sigma'(i)}, v_{\sigma'(j)})$ is an edge of the graph G' , then $i < j$. Extend this map to a function σ of $\{0, 1, \dots, m\}$ by defining $\sigma(i) = \sigma'(i)$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$ and $\sigma(m) = k_r$. Since $v_{k_r} = v_{\sigma(m)}$ has outdegree 0, there is no edge of the form $(v_{\sigma(m)}, v_{\sigma(j)})$ for $j \leq m$. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 1. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a finite directed graph with vertex set $\{v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{m-1}\}$, and let σ be a permutation of $\{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$. Let B_σ be the set of edges $(v_{\sigma(r)}, v_{\sigma(s)}) \in E$ with $r \geq s$. Then the subgraph $G' = (V, E \setminus B_\sigma)$ is acyclic.*

Proof. This follows immediately from Theorem 2. \square

Let $\beta(G)$ denote the minimum size of a set X of edges such that the graph $G' = (V, E \setminus X)$ is directed acyclic.

Corollary 2. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a finite directed graph with vertex set $\{v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{m-1}\}$, and let Σ_m be a set of permutations of $\{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$. For $\sigma \in \Sigma_m$, let B_σ be the set of edges $(v_{\sigma(r)}, v_{\sigma(s)}) \in E$ with $r \geq s$. Then $\beta(G) \leq \min \{\text{card}(B_\sigma) : \sigma \in \Sigma_m\}$.*

Proof. This follows immediately from Corollary 1. \square

Let $\gamma(G)$ denote the number of pairs of nonadjacent vertices in the undirected graph obtained from G by replacing each directed edge with an undirected edge. A *tournament* is a directed graph with no loops and exactly one edge between every two vertices. If G is a tournament, then $\gamma(G) = 0$. Let G be a finite, triangle-free tournament. If G contains directed cycles, then the minimum length n of a directed cycle in G is 4. Let $v_{i_0}, v_{i_1}, v_{i_2}, \dots, v_{i_n}$ be a cycle in G of minimum length n . Since $\gamma(G) = 0$, it follows that either (v_{i_0}, v_{i_2}) or (v_{i_2}, v_{i_0}) is an edge. If (v_{i_0}, v_{i_2}) is an edge, then $v_{i_0}, v_{i_2}, \dots, v_{i_n}$ is a cycle in G of length $n - 1$, which contradicts the minimality of n . If (v_{i_2}, v_{i_0}) is an edge, then $v_{i_0}, v_{i_1}, v_{i_2}$ is a triangle in G , which is impossible. It follows that every finite, triangle-free tournament is directed acyclic. Equivalently, if G is triangle-free and $\gamma(G) = 0$, then $\beta(G) = 0$.

This is a special case of a theorem of Chudnovsky, Seymour, and Sullivan[1], who proved that if G is a triangle-free digraph, then $\beta(G) \leq \gamma(G)$. They conjectured that if G is a triangle-free digraph, then $\beta(G) \leq \gamma(G)/2$.

We shall consider the special case of the CSS conjecture in which the triangle-free graph is a Cayley graph $G = (\mathbb{F}_p, E_A)$ whose vertex set is the additive group of the finite field \mathbf{F}_p and whose edge set E_A is determined by a nonempty subset A of \mathbf{F}_p^* by the following rule:

$$E_A = \{(x, x + a) : x \in \mathbf{F}_p \text{ and } a \in A\}.$$

Let $d = \text{card}(A)$. If the Cayley graph has neither loops nor digons, then the number of pairs of adjacent vertices is the same as the number of directed edges, which is dp , and so the number of pairs of nonadjacent vertices is

$$\gamma(G) = \binom{p}{2} - dp = \frac{p(p-1-2d)}{2}.$$

In this case the CSS conjecture asserts that

$$\beta(G) \leq \frac{p(p-1-2d)}{4}.$$

Lemma 4. *Let p be a prime number and $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d\} \subseteq \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Let $G = (\mathbb{F}_p, E_A)$ be the Cayley graph constructed from A . Let Σ_p be a set of permutations of $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. For $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, define $t_{i,j} \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ by*

$$(\sigma(i) + p\mathbb{Z}) + a_j = \sigma(t_{i,j}) + p\mathbb{Z}.$$

Then $E_A = \{(\sigma(i) + p\mathbb{Z}, \sigma(t_{i,j}) + p\mathbb{Z}) : i = 0, \dots, p-1 \text{ and } j = 1, \dots, d\}$. Let

$$B_\sigma = \{(\sigma(i) + p\mathbb{Z}, \sigma(t_{i,j}) + p\mathbb{Z}) : t_{i,j} < i\}.$$

The graph $G' = (\mathbb{F}_p, E_A \setminus B_\sigma)$ is directed acyclic for every permutation $\sigma \in \Sigma_p$, and

$$\beta(G) \leq \min\{\text{card}(B_\sigma) : \sigma \in \Sigma_p\}.$$

Proof. This follows immediately from Corollary 2. □

Theorem 3. *Let p be prime and $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d\} \subseteq \mathbf{F}_p^*$. Let $G = (\mathbb{F}_p, E_A)$ be the Cayley graph constructed from A . Then $\beta(G) \leq h_p(\langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_d \rangle) \leq \frac{dp}{2}$.*

Proof. Let $\Sigma_p = \{\sigma_k\}_{k=1}^{p-1}$ be the set of permutations of $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ defined by

$$\sigma_k(i) \equiv ki \pmod{p} \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, \dots, p-1.$$

Fix $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. For $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, define $t_{i,j} \in \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\} \setminus \{i\}$ by $(\sigma_k(i) + p\mathbb{Z}) + a_j = \sigma_k(t_{i,j}) + p\mathbb{Z}$. Let u_k denote the least nonnegative integer such that $ku_k \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$. Then $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{p-1}\} = \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$. Defining $r_j = u_k a_j \pmod{p}$, we have $r_j \in \{1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ and $a_j = kr_j + p\mathbb{Z}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_k(t_{i,j}) + p\mathbb{Z} &= (\sigma_k(i) + p\mathbb{Z}) + a_j \\ &= (ki + p\mathbb{Z}) + (kr_j + p\mathbb{Z}) \\ &= k(i + r_j) + p\mathbb{Z} \\ &= \sigma_k(i + r_j) + p\mathbb{Z} \end{aligned}$$

and so $t_{i,j} \equiv i + r_j \pmod{p}$. If $i + r_j \leq p-1$, then $t_{i,j} = i + r_j > i$. If $i + r_j \geq p$, then $t_{i,j} = i + r_j - p < i$. It follows that $t_{i,j} < i$ if and only if $i + r_j \geq p$, that is, $p - r_j \leq i \leq p-1$ and so $\text{card}(B_{\sigma_k}) = \sum_{j=1}^d r_j = \sum_{j=1}^d (u_k a_j \pmod{p})$.

By Corollary 2,

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(G) &\leq \min\{\text{card}(B_{\sigma_k}) : k = 1, \dots, p-1\} = \min \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^d (u_k a_j \pmod p) : k = 1, \dots, p-1 \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^d (k a_j \pmod p) : k = 1, \dots, p-1 \right\} \\ &= h_p(\langle a_1, \dots, a_d \rangle). \end{aligned}$$

The upper bound for the height comes from Lemma 2. □

We return to the CSS conjecture. Since $dp/2 \leq p(p-1-2d)/4$ if and only if $d \leq (p-1)/4$, it follows that, for a fixed prime p , we only need to consider sets A of cardinality $d > p/4$. In the other direction, Hamidoune [2, 3] proved the Caccetta-Haggkvist conjecture for Cayley graphs: If $A \subseteq \mathbf{F}_p^*$ and $d = |A| \geq p/r$, then the Cayley graph (\mathbf{F}_p, E_A) contains a cycle of length no greater than r . In particular, if the graph has no directed loops, digons, or triangles, then $d < p/3$. Therefore, to prove the CSS conjecture for the group \mathbf{F}_p , it suffices to consider only sets A of size d , where $p/4 < d < p/3$.

The following result uses heights to prove a special case of the CSS conjecture.

Theorem 4. *Let p be a prime number, $p \geq 7$, and let $A = \{a_1, a_2\} \subseteq \mathbf{F}_p^*$ with $a_1 \neq a_2$. Let $G = (\mathbf{F}_p, E_A)$ be the Cayley graph constructed from A . If G is a triangle-free digraph, then*

$$\beta(G) \leq \frac{p-1}{2} \leq \frac{\gamma(G)}{2}.$$

Proof. Since $\langle a_1, a_2 \rangle = \langle 1 + p\mathbb{Z}, a \rangle$ in $\mathbb{P}^1(\mathbf{F}_p)$ with $a = a_1^{-1}a_2 \neq 1 + p\mathbb{Z}$, and since $\beta(G) \leq h_p(\langle a_1, a_2 \rangle) = h_p(\langle 1 + p\mathbb{Z}, a \rangle)$, it suffices to consider the case $A = \{1 + p\mathbb{Z}, a\}$. The Cayley graph G is triangle-free if and only if none of the equations

$$x = p\mathbb{Z}, \quad x + y = p\mathbb{Z}, \quad \text{and} \quad x + y + z = p\mathbb{Z}$$

has a solution with $x, y, z \in \{1 + p\mathbb{Z}, a\}$. The first equation implies that $a \neq p\mathbb{Z}$, the second that $a \neq p-1 + p\mathbb{Z}$, and that third that $2a + 1 \neq p\mathbb{Z}$ and $a + 2 \neq p\mathbb{Z}$, or, equivalently, that $a \neq (p-1)/2 + p\mathbb{Z}$ or $p-2 + p\mathbb{Z}$. It follows from Theorem 1 that

$$\beta(G) \leq h_p(\langle 1 + p\mathbb{Z}, a \rangle) \leq \frac{p-1}{2} \leq \frac{p(p-5)}{4} = \frac{\gamma(G)}{2}$$

if $p \geq 7$. This completes the proof. □

References

- [1] M. Chudnovsky, P. Seymour, and B. Sullivan, *Cycles in dense digraphs*, arXiv:math.CO/0702147, 2007.
- [2] Y. O. Hamidoune, *An application of connectivity theory in graphs to factorizations of elements in groups*, European J. Combin. **2** (1981), no. 4, 349-355.
- [3] M. B. Nathanson, *The Caccetta-Haggkvist conjecture and additive number theory*, arXiv:math.CO/0603469, 2006.